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The Problem of Conserving Medieval Paintings on Exteriors in Slovenia

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- still visible on exterior
- wall painting removed
- disintegrated or whitewashed over
- now in interior

Vse znane lokacije srednjeveških stenskih slik na zunanjsčinah v Sloveniji (z modrimi točkami so označene tudi tiste lokacije objektov, ki imajo poleg še vidnih tudi snete, propadle, prebeljene ali sedaj v notranjsčinah nahajajoče se poslikave); Avtor: B. Šeme, 2005.

All known locations of medieval wall paintings on exteriors in Slovenia (the dark blue circles also indicate those locations that in addition to still-visible paintings have paintings that have disintegrated, been whitewashed over or removed, or are now located in interiors); Author: B. Šeme, 2005.

Reka, podružnična cerkev sv. Kancijana, južna zunanjsčina, sv. Krištof; primer številčnega ocenjevanja ohranjenosti barvne plasti stenske slike od 1 (le še redki ostanki barvne plasti na originalnem ometu) do 5. V tem primeru je mogoče reči, da je barvna plast ohranjena do tretje ozroma četrte stopnje, čeprav je ta podatek lahko zavajajoč, saj je tako dobro ohranjenih morda le okoli 10 odstotkov celotne poslikave (foto: B. Šeme, 2003).

Reka, St Canzian's Church, south wall, St Christopher; example of numerical assessment of state of conservation of the paint layer of a wall painting from 1 (only a few remnants of the paint layer on the original plaster) to 5. In this case it is possible to say that the paint layer is conserved to the third or fourth degree, although this figure can be misleading, since perhaps only 10 per cent of the whole painting is this well conserved (photo: B. Šeme, 2003).

Razvrstitev srednjeveških stenskih slik na zunanjščinah glede na stopnjo ohranjenosti barvne plasti. Predstavljen je rezultat številčnega ocenjevanja od 0 do 5 (avtor: B. Š).

Classification of medieval wall paintings on exteriors in Slovenia by degree of conservation of the paint layer. The result of numerical assessment from 0 to 5 is shown (author: B. Š).

Valterski Vrh, podružnična cerkev sv. Filipa in Jakoba, zahodna stena prezbiterija, sv. Krištof, detajl; pojav lišajev in zelo gosta mreža razpok v intonaku, razpok je manj na svetlejši površini (foto: B. Š., 2003).

Valterski Vrh, Church of St Philip and St James, west wall of the sanctuary, St Christopher, detail; lichens and a very dense network of cracks in the intonaco; there are fewer cracks in the lighter surface (photo: B. Š., 2003).

Orientiranost srednjeveških stenskih slik na zunanjsčinah v Sloveniji (avtor: B. Š.)

Orientation of medieval wall paintings on exteriors in Slovenia (author: B. Š.)

Pojav s prostim očesom vidnih mikroorganizmov (predvsem lišajev in alg) na srednjeveških stenskih slikah na zunanjsčinah v Sloveniji glede na orientiranost stenskih slik (avtor: B. Š.)

Appearance of microorganisms (mainly lichens and algae) visible to the naked eye on mediaeval wall paintings on exteriors in Slovenia with regard to the orientation of the paintings (author: B. Š.)

Pojav s prostim očesom vidnih mikroorganizmov (predvsem lišajev in alg) na srednjeveških stenskih slikah na zunanjsčinah v Sloveniji glede na zaščitenost stenskih slik pred padavinami in sončnim obsevanjem (avtor: B. Š.)

Appearance of microorganisms (mainly lichens and algae) visible to the naked eye on mediaeval wall paintings on exteriors in Slovenia with regard to the protection of the paintings from precipitation and sunlight (author: B. Š.) of numerical assessment from 0 to 5 is shown (author: B. Š.).

pred 1936

2003

Ribčev Laz, podružnična cerkev sv. Janeza Krstnika, južna zunanjsčina, sv. Krištof; primerjava fotografij stanja poslikave pred letom 1936 (vir foto: Stele, 1935) in v letu 2003 (foto: B. Š.)

Ribčev Laz, Church of St John the Baptist, south wall, St Christopher; comparison of photographs of the state of the painting before 1936 (left; source of photo: Stele, 1935) and in 2003 (right; photo: B. Š.).

Brod v Bohinju, podružnična cerkev sv. Marije Magdalene, južna zunanjščina, sv. Krištof; poenostavljena razdelitev stenske slike na tri dele glede na različne naravne dejavnike ogrožanja – zgornji del poslikave ogrožajo manj škodljivi dejavniki (pod pogojem, da ne prihaja do zamakanja streh, napak v napeljavi ipd.), kot so kondenzna vlaga, onesnaženo ozračje, mikroorganizmi. V srednjem delu se dodatno pojavi močan vpliv padavin. Spodnje dele, poleg naštetih dejavnikov, ogroža še kapilarna vlaga z vodotopnimi solmi (foto: B. Š., 2003).

Brod v Bohinju, Church of St Mary Magdalene, south wall, St Christopher; simplified division of the wall painting into three parts with regard to different natural risk factors – the upper part of the painting is at risk from less harmful factors (provided no water infiltration of the roofs or drainage defects occur, etc.) such as condensation damp, air pollution, microorganisms. In the middle section precipitation has a strong effect. As well as from the other factors mentioned, the lower sections are at risk from capillary damp with water-soluble salts (photo: B. Š., 2003).

Blaž Šeme

The Problem of Conserving Medieval Paintings on Exteriors in Slovenia

Keywords: art, wall painting, frescoes, art heritage, exteriors, conservation-restoration, conservation methodology, recording of condition, Middle Ages, Gothic

Abstract

The numerous paintings on the façades of churches, chapels, monuments, castles, town houses and rural houses demonstrate that the custom of decorating exteriors was widespread in Slovenia from the Middle Ages onwards. This segment of open-air artistic heritage is usually badly exposed to harmful natural and human environmental factors and is therefore one of the heritage types most at risk. With a suitably methodologically supported protection strategy it is possible to monitor the extent, state of conservation and risk status of wall paintings and take timely steps to protect them. To this end an experimental project has been designed, within the framework of which a model of an integrated approach to conserving wall paintings has been developed and applied. The result of the collection of data in the field and in historical records is an extensive database on the state of conservation and the risk status of more than 200 medieval wall paintings on the exteriors of more than 130 buildings. Some of the more important data on the condition of this segment of heritage are presented in this paper.

The model is sufficiently broad to be applicable to both interior and exterior wall paintings and, with suitable adjustments, to other segments of art heritage. It can be linked to the methodologies of related disciplines (architecture, ethnology, archaeology, etc.) and its results can be incorporated into a corresponding cultural heritage information system.

The phenomenon of medieval wall paintings on exteriors

In the Late Middle Ages the tradition of decorating exteriors was widespread in the wider Alpine and pre-Alpine area. This applies in particular to northern Friuli and South Tyrol.¹ In Slovenia too, something over two hundred locations are known, for the most part on the exteriors of religious buildings that were adorned with figural depictions in the Middle Ages. This, however, probably represents just a fraction of an originally much larger number of buildings with painted exteriors, for the most part in Gorenjska (Upper Carniola), Central Slovenia and Dolenjska (Lower Carniola). Today two thirds of all known medieval

wall paintings are still visible, at least as traces, on exteriors. The others have decayed or been destroyed or are hidden beneath layers of whitewash and plaster. There are also some wall paintings that have been removed from their original positions, and a few locations where, as a result of various remodellings of buildings, they are now visible in interiors (Fig. 1).

The most commonly painted motif on exteriors is St Christopher, who was depicted in almost half of all the known locations in Slovenia. This motif is followed by depictions of Christ's Passion and the Virgin Mary in numerous variants and by St George on a horse. A small number of these works of art were painted between the end of the 13th century and the end of the 14th century. The remainder date from the 15th century and the first half of the 16th century and already show varying degrees of Renaissance influence. It is possible to determine at least approximately the authorship of slightly over half of the wall paintings. The majority of them are the work of Italian travelling workshops (from the Gorizia area or the wider Friuli region) or were created under their influence. A large proportion are by Bartholomeus (Jernej) of Loka, while the influence of other painters or workshops is considerably smaller. More than half of the buildings with paintings on their exterior also have medieval paintings in their interior.²

The basic purpose of paintings on the exteriors (and interiors) of religious buildings was to instruct, encourage faith and remind the observer of Christ's sacrifice and the examples of the saints. Some depictions, for example those of St Christopher, at the same time protected against misfortune. Today this original function of wall paintings has already faded to a considerable extent, and their physical integrity is similarly faded and damaged. But although many of them can no longer be admired in unspoilt form in the aesthetic sense, they still have significant historical value. And if we recognise them as works of art with an aesthetic and historical nature, it is also vital that we ensure that they are suitably preserved.³

The approach to the conservation of cultural heritage should be as comprehensive as possible: a complete inventory, identification and analysis of condition and risk status, timely and suitable intervention, constant observation and monitoring, and so on. Such an approach is especially necessary when we are dealing with an at-risk segment of heritage like exterior wall paintings.

General assessment of the state of conservation

The condition of medieval wall paintings still visible on exteriors⁴ varies in terms of extent and state of conservation. For a general assessment of condition, the two most important data are the extent of conservation of the original plaster and the state of conservation of the paint layer. Assessment of condition is made more difficult by a number of factors: frequent secondary applications (plaster, whitewash, biological growth, salts, dirt, etc.), non-uniform conservation (in the assessment of the state of conservation of the paint layer), various types of damage (e.g. flaking, crumbling and fading of the paint layer) and the subjectivity of assessment (Fig. 2).

The results of analysis show that in less than a third of wall paintings does a large extent of the original plaster survive (meaning that more than three quarters of the original painted plaster has been conserved). The high proportion of indeterminableness (more

than a third of all paintings) is a result of the fact that many wall paintings are to a large extent covered by secondary applications. In general, the assessment of condition is more influenced by data on the state of conservation of the paint layer. It has been shown that slightly less than a tenth of the paintings are relatively well conserved and do not require direct interventions. All they need is suitable maintenance, effective protection against potential harmful environmental impacts and regular checking. On the other hand, a similar number of paintings have already practically disintegrated, since, with the exception of the original plaster, practically no traces of the original painting are still visible. Nevertheless, the plaster can still be a valuable source for the analysis of historical materials and it would be a shame to reject it without taking samples. The great majority of the remaining wall paintings lie somewhere between these two extremes in terms of the state of conservation of the paint layer and it is precisely in this segment of exterior wall paintings that the most difficult questions are raised as regards their suitable conservation in the future (Fig. 3).

A general assessment is insufficient for a more accurate analysis of condition. It is also necessary to collect data on the painting technique and technology employed, the history of the buildings and their paintings, types of damage, exposure to harmful factors, the dynamics of deterioration and types and level of risk. I shall cite just a few of the most important data collected during the project of recording the state of conservation and risk status of medieval wall paintings on exteriors in Slovenia.⁵

Painting technique and technology

Medieval wall paintings on exteriors in Slovenia are typically painted on a stone support, which is usually covered by two or, more rarely, three layers of plaster. Only in the lunettes of the portals of St James's Church in Kostanjevica na Krki and the Church of the Assumption in Lesce are the paintings applied directly to the stone support.

The appearance of the plaster varies according to the type of lime used and, above all, the type of aggregate, which can be river sand or crushed rock. Additives of various types can often be observed in plasters. These were added to give greater solidity or resistance or to make the plaster dry more slowly following application. The most frequent additives are crushed brick (recorded in at least twenty-five locations) and particles of unslaked lime (at least sixteen locations), and sometimes grains of charcoal. The paintings were usually done in a combined technique, meaning that parts of them were painted using a fresco technique (the most durable parts), while specific sections were additionally painted a secco. The painters made frequent use of sinopie, preliminary sketches and underpainting, although these are often hard to detect with the naked eye.

Most commonly, a palette of earth colours was used: yellow ochre, sienna, umber, red oxide, green earth. For the blue and green parts of paintings, artists could also make limited use of more expensive pigments such as azurite and malachite, which were less durable. For other colours, too, they used pigments that were less resistant to air, light, the base environment (lime) or contact with other pigments and substances. Black or dark brown sections where we would expect to see light colour fields (for example the painted halos in Mače and Zabočevo and on the garments at Sveti Križ and Ljubno ob Savinji) allow us to conclude that lead yellow or lead white pigments were actually used, and then later grew darker.⁶ It is also possible to observe imprints, especially of halos on saints, outlines

of drawings and stencils on borders, clothes and backgrounds and, more rarely, applications.⁷

History of the buildings and their paintings

Over the course of history the buildings have been damaged, destroyed, renovated and converted. The reasons for this vary: maltreatment, maintenance and protection, natural disasters and human interventions or simple changes in taste and changes of era. Of the various renovations and conversions, those most harmful to the wall paintings that are still visible on exteriors have been the demolition of walls, the building of extensions (e.g. bell towers, porches, sacristies, chapels) and the opening or widening of windows and doors. The most frequent harmful interventions are newly added or enlarged windows. These have damaged approximately a fifth of all medieval wall paintings still visible on exteriors. Changes to buildings and, indirectly, to paintings also occur during regular or preventive maintenance: reproofing, plastering and whitewashing, structural reinforcements, installation of drainage systems, waterproofing, etc.

For various reasons some wall paintings were renovated, overpainted or covered with plasters and whitewashes soon after being created. Even by the end of the Middle Ages there were painters in Slovenia whose regular work included the renovation of wall paintings – for example Bartholomeus (Jernej) of Loka and the anonymous Master Painter of Podpeč. They were not restorers in the modern sense of the word, but were employed to “freshen up” or repaint old, faded images. Sometimes they simply cut out old wall paintings and then applied plaster for a new painting. At St John’s Church in Bohinj, traces of three medieval depictions of St Christopher can be seen on the south wall of the church, one on top of the other.

More than a fifth of all exterior wall paintings have been cut out, which is a reliable indication that they were once covered with plaster. Less serious damage is caused by covering with layers of whitewash. Today approximately 60 per cent of wall paintings have been fully or mostly uncovered, but it is interesting to note that at the beginning of the last century more than 80 per cent of all paintings visible today were still hidden beneath layers of whitewash and plaster. Sometimes major mechanical damage has occurred during the uncovering of wall paintings.

At least two thirds of all paintings have also undergone some form of restoration in recent years.

State of conservation with regard to types of damage

Among the more common types of damage to exterior wall paintings is mechanical damage, especially cracked plaster and poor adhesiveness/cohesiveness of the plaster and the paint layer. This damage occurs above all as the result of the natural environmental factors (precipitation, damp, temperature fluctuations, movements of the air, etc.) to which exterior wall paintings are constantly exposed. Mechanical damage has a significant effect on the general assessment of the state of conservation of exterior wall paintings and on the assessment of their risk status.

In three quarters of all paintings there is medium to very severe crumbling or flaking of the paint layer and point flaking of the pictorial layer of the plaster. The phenomenon of point flaking in medieval exterior wall paintings is severe or perceptible in almost all cases where crushed brick particles or grains of unslaked lime are used as an additive in the plaster. In some cases it is possible to observe characteristic eruptions up to a centimetre long at the bottom of which are crushed brick fragments (e.g. Gorenje Karteljevo, Malo Črnelo, Zalog) or particles of unslaked lime (e.g. Podvrh nad Javorjami).

More serious, deeper cracks originating from movements of the support are rare in medieval exterior wall paintings. The clearest example of larger cracks is in the wall painting on St Canzian's Church in Reka pri Cerknem. Smaller cracks deriving from the plaster itself vary greatly in shape. Especially problematic are the more infrequent but deeper cracks (these can appear in all the layers of the plaster) and dense networks of shallower cracks in the intonaco. It has become apparent that the phenomenon of a very dense network of cracks is most often closely connected to the phenomenon of microorganisms. A clear example of this are the deep cracks and simultaneous presence of microorganisms (lichens) on the surface of the painting of St Christopher on the exterior sanctuary wall at Valterski Vrh (Fig 4).

In several cases it has been possible to observe fallen pieces of plaster on the ground (e.g. Gosteče, Gorenja Dobrava, Krvava Peč, Kuren, Tlake, Visoko, Zanigrad). This draws attention to the greater danger faced by these paintings.

Exposure to harmful environmental factors

An important factor for the assessment of the risk status of a painting is exposure, which depends on the position of the building, the location of the painting on the building and the protection of the painting from harmful environmental factors.

Exact information on the position of the building helps in establishing the risks to the building and the painting as a result of various geographically conditioned factors: weather conditions, air pollution, risk of earthquake and flood and other threats. It has for example been established that a small number of locations are characterised by a Mediterranean climate (Zanigrad, Podgorje, Krasno, Prilesje), an Alpine climate (Rateče, Podkoren, Ribčev Laz, Stara Fužina, Brod, Jezersko and Solčava) or a continental climate (Gorenje Karteljevo, Štatenberk, Hmeljčič, Gorenji Mokronog, Gorenje Jesenice, Žunovec and Martjanci). Other locations are on the margin of the last two of these climate areas and even more frequently within an area with a sub-Alpine and Dinaric climate.

The position (height and orientation) of the painting on the building and protection against constant harmful environmental factors have a significant influence on the risk status of paintings. Research to date has shown that paintings on south-facing walls are slightly more resistant to harmful environmental factors. It is surprising that almost half of the surviving paintings are on south-facing exteriors, while the smallest number – just ten recorded paintings – are on east-facing walls (Fig. 5). This raises the question of whether this is the result of the greater resistance of south-facing paintings or an indication that medieval painters were already aware of this fact and therefore avoided non-south-facing walls. Regardless of orientation, the lower parts of paintings (one to two metres above the ground) are badly damaged by rising damp and the carrying of water-soluble substances

into the walls. In some places this problem is addressed by drainage or air channels, although in the field it is often difficult to recognise these measures, together with any waterproofing.

Another very important threat factor is precipitation and wind. The level of exposure and protection from precipitation and wind are important. Two thirds of all paintings are beneath overhanging roofs and 8 per cent are without any protection at all. The other open-air paintings are beneath roofs (in open porches, bell towers, chapels, monuments) or on façades with additional protection (sunk in the wall, additional projecting roofs and overhangs). In some places even an additional projecting roof fails to provide sufficient protection, as can be concluded in the case of the paintings on the sanctuary of St Elizabeth's Church in Ljubno ob Savinji, where a damaged lip on the projecting roof allows rainwater to slide down the painting.

Approximately two fifths of all medieval exterior wall paintings are exposed to direct sunlight, which is not surprising considering that a large proportion of wall paintings are south-facing.

Dynamics of deterioration

For an approximate assessment of the dynamics of deterioration it is enough to compare older photo-documentation of the paintings with their state today. A comparison of photographs of varying quality taken in different periods and conditions suffices to provide a rough assessment of changes, particularly in the case of major damage. A number of difficulties and limitations do however need to be taken into account:

- different types of photographs (different types of film, lighting, angles, etc.),
- possible harmful dampening of the wall before photographing, which gives an unrealistic picture of changes to the paint layer,
- only certain types of damage can be perceived,
- too few data about past interventions and their effectiveness,
- too little quality old photo-documentation is available, or cannot be dated.

By studying old photographic material it was established that a decade or two is often not enough to reveal major changes in the state of conservation of the paint layer that are visible to the naked eye (much depends here on the position and protection of the painting), while a comparison with photographs taken before the Second World War usually indicates worrying differences in the state of conservation. For a telling illustration of worrying changes it is enough to compare the situation in Stele's photographs, published in 1935,⁸ with the present state (e.g. the paintings on the exteriors of churches in Ribčev Laz in Bohinj, Mače pri Preddvoru, Bodešče, Žužemberk, Visoko, etc.). (Fig. 8)

A more accurate and objective method involves periodic measurements of changes of state with the help of accurate optical instruments, although this method has not yet been used in Slovenia, or at least not to any large extent.⁹ The method enables us to perceive three main types of change and damage to wall paintings (according to G. Thomson¹⁰):

- cracks, flaking and crumbling of plaster and the paint layer,
- surface filling,
- colour changes.

There are also too few data on meteorological or (micro-)climatic measurements (e.g. precipitation, wind, moisture in the air, sunlight) and measurements of damp in the wall.

General assessment of risk status

Exterior wall paintings, like other cultural heritage, are basically threatened by three types of factors: natural environmental factors, natural disasters and human interventions.

The human factor is the most unpredictable. The general assessment of the current situation is that neglect and inappropriate or non-expert interventions are more of a threat to wall paintings than vandalism. Among natural disasters, the risk of earthquake is one of the more important factors, since the majority of locations are in an area with a considerable risk of seismic activity. Other natural disasters are also possible: floods, droughts, fires, landslides, erosion, heavy snowfall, etc.

Most attention has been devoted to establishing the threat from natural environmental factors, since today these factors are the most common cause of deterioration of exterior wall paintings. Natural risk factors are generally easier to control, since they are more predictable. The only difficulty is that they usually cause slow but steady changes that are relatively hard to observe over a short period. With regard to threats to exterior wall paintings, the following findings can be offered:

The clearest threat factor is water in various forms, especially precipitation in poorly protected or wind-exposed locations, and rising damp as the result of capillary action together with the water-soluble salts that the damp carries with it. Furthermore, major temperature fluctuations, especially below and above 0°C are a major threat to walls and plaster with an excessive moisture content. Additional threats in the case of precipitation are acid rain (chemical changes) and hail (mechanical damage).

Precipitation and wind

In general those paintings protected by short overhangs or merely short roof edges are more at risk. A more accurate definition of the most at-risk segment of paintings would however require more accurate analysis, for example of the angle of protection of an individual painting and the direction and force of winds in locations with wall paintings. Furthermore many extended overhangs or additional projecting roofs do not protect the lower parts of paintings.

Capillary damp and water-soluble salts

The extent of the threat to wall paintings from capillary damp is almost impossible to determine with the naked eye. Precise measurements of damp in the wall and a review of documentation on any existing drainage systems, drying and insulating of walls and waterproofing are necessary. In general it is only possible to say that wall paintings on the lower parts of walls, close to the ground, are more at risk.

Two slightly less conspicuous natural threats are condensation damp combined with air pollution and direct sunlight (Fig. 9).

Conclusion

Despite the presence of numerous harmful factors, a significant proportion of medieval wall paintings on exteriors have survived to the present day, although in less than perfect condition. The conservation of these works of art is problematic because of the greater threat deriving from harmful environmental factors and the frequently worsening condition and inadequate control of the situation. Owing to their poor state of conservation, many of them are hard to decipher in both the artistic/aesthetic sense and in the iconographic and symbolic sense. They are frequently merely very faded or fragmentary remains of a painting.

In the case of well-conserved and well-protected wall paintings, suitable protection and preventive conservation are usually enough, and direct interventions on the original (except strengthening, hydrophobisation, applications of biocides, etc.) are unnecessary. Where paintings are less well conserved, other solutions are possible on a case by case basis. These include direct interventions on the work of art:

- conservation *in situ* with aesthetic touching-up not just of lacunae but also of the original (e.g. Pijava Gorica, Spodnje Bitnje, Spodnji Otok),
- covering with a protective layer of whitewash or plaster (recently, for example, Knežja Njiva, Vrzdenc, Žunovec) and if possible a painted copy or reconstruction over this (there is no example of this technique in Slovenia),
- removal of the wall painting and transfer to another location and if possible a painted copy or reconstruction in the original location (Vrzdenc, Vihre, Visoko pod Kureščkom, Stari trg pri Slovenj Gradcu).

In deciding on the method of conservation, systematic analysis of the condition and past interventions based on an integrated, methodologically supported protection strategy with constant collection of data on the situation in the field, archive sources and simple access to them can be very helpful. Data collected in this way are not only useful for those who are directly involved with protection but also for a wider circle of researchers both from the field of the humanities (historians, art historians, ethnologists, archaeologists, etc.) and from scientific and technical disciplines (builders, architects, chemists, biologists, physicists, meteorologists, etc.).

Use of the model for monitoring the state of conservation and risk status of wall paintings has only provided a partial analysis of data on the state of conservation of medieval exterior wall paintings in Slovenia, which nevertheless is producing promising results. It would therefore be worth considering widening the use of the model to other segments of wall paintings, both interior and exterior and, with appropriate modifications, to other segments of art heritage.

In 2006 the model was also successfully tested outside Slovenia. Through analysis of the condition of sixteenth-century wall paintings on the exteriors and interiors of ten churches in Moldavia (NE Romania), seven of which are on UNESCO's World Heritage List,¹¹ I obtained important new data connected to the problem of conserving exterior wall paintings. The data were obtained through investigation of the condition of the churches on the ground and analysis of archive sources in Bucharest and at ICCROM in Rome.

Notes

- 1 Robert Peskar, *Srednjeveške poslikave zunanjščin cerkva v osrednji Sloveniji*, degree thesis, University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana 1991, p. 12.
- 2 Almost 400 buildings with medieval wall paintings (interior or exterior) are known in Slovenia, judging from the lists published in: Janez Höfler, *Srednjeveške freske v Sloveniji*, Books I, II, III and IV (Höfler 1996, Höfler 1997, Höfler 2001 and Höfler 2004).
- 3 Cf. Cesare Brandi, *Theory of Restoration*, Florence 2005, p. 49.
- 4 Currently 138 structures with 205 painted units on their exteriors have been recorded.
- 5 Blaž Šeme, *Metoda ugotavljanja ohranjenosti in ogroženosti stenskih poslikav na zunanjščinah v Sloveniji na izbranem segmentu*, doctoral dissertation, University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana 2005. (Mentor Prof. Ivan Bogovčič, co-mentor Assoc. Prof. Roko Žarnić).
- 6 This could also be the result of a darkened basis for gilding, although this seems less likely. Only accurate laboratory analysis of samples would give a more reliable answer.
- 7 More on techniques in: Anabelle Križnar, *Slog in tehnika srednjeveškega stenskega slikarstva na Slovenskem*, doctoral dissertation, University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana 2004 (published in book form in 2006).
- 8 France Stele, *Monumenta artis slovenicae I. Srednjeveško stensko slikarstvo*, Ljubljana 1935.
- 9 As part of the project various methods of scientific investigation were applied at St Canzian's Church in Vrzenec during 2004 and 2005 with experts from various institutions (Regional Units of the Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia, the Restoration Centre, the Building and Civil Engineering Institute of Slovenia, the Institute for Research into Materials and Structures, the Jožef Stefan Institute, the Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering, the Biotechnology Faculty, the Faculty of Natural Sciences and Engineering and the Academy of Fine Arts). These included experimental measurement of colour fading with the help of spectrophotometry. Gorazd Golob of the Textiles Department of the Faculty of Natural Sciences and Engineering in Ljubljana Textiles collaborated on the measurements.
- 10 R. M. Lemaire, P. Mora, G. Thomson, P. Philippot, *La conservation des peintures murales en Moldavie*. (29 October–6 November 1970). 20. Rome: ICCROM, 1970.
- 11 These are the churches in Probota, Pătrăuți, Voroneț, Arbore, Suceava, Humor and Moldovița.